
MEDIATING ROLE OF FRUSTRATION BETWEEN COGNITIVE DISTORTIONS AND INTERNET ADDICTION AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS OF UNIVERSITIES IN MAKURDI, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the mediating role of frustration between cognitive distortions and internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. Accidental sampling technique was used in sampling three hundred and eighty-one (381) participants from two (2) universities (Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University and Benue State University) in Makurdi. Their ages ranged from 20 to 32 years with a mean score of 26.055 years (SD=2.361). Cognitive Distortions Scale, Frustration Discomfort Scale and Internet Addiction Test were used for data collection. Four hypotheses were formulated and tested using multiple linear regression analysis, simple linear regression analysis, Hayes process mediation analysis and Hierarchical regression analysis. The result revealed a significant positive influence of cognitive distortions on internet addiction among undergraduate students. The results also revealed a significant positive influence of frustration on internet addiction among undergraduate students. Furthermore, hypothesis three revealed a significant mediating effect of frustration between cognitive distortions and internet addiction among undergraduate students. Finally, there was a significant joint influence of cognitive distortions and frustration on internet addiction among students when age, sex and level of income were controlled. The study therefore recommended among others that stakeholders, including the government and educational policymakers, should design and fund awareness programmes highlighting the dangers of internet addiction and how cognitive distortions and frustration contribute to it.

Key Words: Cognitive Distortions, Frustration, Internet Addiction, Undergraduate Students

Introduction

As a rising trend in the world, internet-based research has become vital in the daily life of humans. The use of the internet has increased in recent years and has become an important part of life for the general population. The internet has evolved in the early 1980s, revolutionizing broadcasting, information sharing and connecting individuals worldwide. Over the past decade, the internet has become an integral part of life for most people (Anastasia & Henry, 2017). With the sophistication of the latest technology, the use of the internet is continually expanding. The internet began to gain people's trust as a sophisticated technological tool that can be applied widely, but carries both positive and negative impacts in terms of its use in modern lifestyle (Ying-Ying et al., 2021). Today, the internet can be used for teaching, learning, research, gaming, online gambling and watching sexually explicit material, and as a mode of connecting people through texting, calling, social websites, chat applications, and e-mails (Ginige, 2017).

Although the drastic increase in the use of the internet has truly benefited its users, excessive or uncontrollable use has created social, psychological and behavioural disorders (Azmi et al., 2020). In Africa, internet usage among students is rapidly growing, although it lags behind global averages due to challenges such as limited infrastructure, high costs, and uneven access. As of 2024, about 40-50% of university students across the continent regularly use the internet for their studies. The figures vary widely by country, with higher penetration rates in countries like South Africa, Kenya, and Egypt, where internet infrastructure is more developed. In Nigeria, internet usage among university students is relatively high compared to many other African nations, driven by the widespread adoption of smartphones and mobile internet. Around 60% of Nigerian university students are reported to have regular access to the internet with some using it primarily for academic research, social networking, and accessing online learning platforms (Bhuiyan & Khan, 2024).

The excessive use of the internet among university students has been linked to several factors, one of which is cognitive distortions: irrational and biased ways of thinking that significantly contribute to various forms of addiction, including internet addiction. Cognitive distortions are persistent thought patterns that distort reality, often leading to negative emotional states such as anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem (Shek et al., 2023). These emotional states drive students to seek out coping mechanisms, one of which may involve the overuse of the internet. Cognitive distortions such as catastrophizing and overgeneralization among others play particularly compelling roles in this process.

Similarly, one other key emotional trigger that can contribute to the development of internet addiction is frustration; which is a negative emotional state that arises when an individual feels blocked from achieving a desired goal. Frustration occurs when an individual's efforts to achieve a goal are thwarted, leading to feelings of anger, annoyance, and helplessness (Pontes et al., 2016). This emotional state can be particularly intense among university students, who often face high academic pressures, social challenges, and uncertainties about the future. When students experience frustration, they may seek out ways to alleviate these negative feelings, and the internet can provide an immediate, albeit temporary, escape from their problems (Chen & Nath, 2016; Kuss et al., 2018). Studies have shown that frustration is a significant predictor of internet addiction (Kuss et al., 2018). When individuals experience frustration, they may turn to the internet as a means of escaping or avoiding the negative emotions associated with their unmet goals. This is particularly true for university students, who may use the internet to distract themselves from academic challenges or social difficulties (Pontes et al., 2016).

Cognitive Distortions and Internet Addiction

Agnihotri and Datti (2023) examined the relationship between problematic Internet use (PIU) and cognitive distortions among university students. Data was collected from 387 students from Andhra Pradesh, India. Generalized Problematic Internet Use Scale-2 (GPIUS-2) and Cognitive Distortions Questionnaire were employed to gather responses. Family size, education level, and average time of internet use during COVID-19 were discovered to be key elements for GPIUS-2 and GPIUS-2 components (negative outcomes, cognitive preoccupation, and mood regulation). Pearson correlation showed a strong positive relationship between problematic internet use (PIU) and cognitive distortions. A simple linear regression analysis was performed in which the PIU scores were predicted based on cognitive distortions, and it was found that cognitive distortions predicted PIU.

Ozparlak et al. (2022) examined differences in the levels of internet addiction across internet activities, and the associations of cognitive distortions with internet addiction and internet activities. This is a cross-sectional study involving 638 adolescents. Data were collected using a personal information form, the Internet Addiction Scale and The Children's Negative Cognitive Error Questionnaire. Data were analyzed using SPSSv23 and descriptive methods, independent samples *t*-test, linear regression, logistic regression were performed. The prevalence of internet addiction in adolescents was found to be 16.9%. The internet addiction scores of adolescents who use the internet for online gaming, visiting pornographic sites, using and chatting on social media, and aimless browsing are higher. Catastrophizing, personalization, and selective abstraction cognitive distortions explain internet addiction variance at a level of 17.5%. Selective abstraction predicts online gaming and aimless browsing, personalization predicts pornographic site visiting, and catastrophization predicts doing homework on the internet. Online gaming, visiting pornographic sites, using and chatting on social media and internet aimless browsing are distinctive of internet addiction. Internet addiction and various internet activities are associated with cognitive distortions.

Mackey and Hodgins (2022) examined the role of cognitive distortions in Internet gambling. The primary objectives were to determine whether cognitive distortions predict Internet gambling and investigate whether distorted gambling-related cognitions are associated with problem gambling severity among online gamblers. Three hundred and seventy four undergraduate participants (143 online gamblers, 172 males) completed an online questionnaire looking at demographics, play-related variables (duration, frequency and expenditures of play) and cognitive distortions. Variables were entered into a logistic regression model to predict online gambling. Three variables made independent contributions to predicting Internet gambling: male gender, higher frequency of play, and cognitive distortions. A hierarchical linear regression analysis with internet gamblers revealed that cognitive distortions accounted for a proportion of the variance in problem gambling severity beyond variance accounted for by demographic variables and level of gambling involvement.

Frustration and Internet Addiction

Aat et al. (2022) conducted a study to analyze the correlation between academic frustration and internet addiction in adolescents. The cross-sectional technique was utilized in this study, which included 378 students from five public high schools in Garut, West Java, Indonesia. Probability sampling with proportionate stratified random sampling was utilized as the sampling approach. The instruments used are the Internet Addiction Test (IAT) and the Educational Stress Scale for Adolescents (ESSA). The Spearman ranking correlation test was used to examine the data. The results showed that the amount of time spent on the internet on weekdays was <6 hours/day (67.7%), while on weekends it increased to >6 hours/day (71.2%). Internet use in adolescents was normal (51.1%), and of mild dependence (39.7%).

The adolescents had moderate stress levels (76.5%) and high stress levels (19%). Academic stress and internet addiction are significantly associated among adolescents (p-value 0.01). Academic frustration, it may be concluded, is significantly related with internet addiction in adolescents.

Kawal and Shafi (2015) assessed internet addiction and psychological distress among university students. The sample in the study consisted of one hundred university students out of which 61 were males and 39 were females who were selected on the purposive basis from the main campus of Kashmir University. Young's Internet Addiction Scale (IAT), Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10) and Demographic Data sheet were used to collect research data from informants. The obtained data were analyzed by frequency method, Pearson correlation method and t-test. The results revealed that male university students experienced more internet addiction and psychological distress as compared to the female university students and a significant positive correlation was found between internet addiction and psychological distress among university students. Moreover, the results also indicated that rural university students experienced more internet addiction and psychological distress as compared to urban university students. The study included only one hundred university students, which is a relatively small sample size. The present study sampled three hundred and eighty-one university students which is more reliable for generalization.

Cognitive Distortion, Frustration and Internet Addiction

Benedetto et al. (2024) investigated cognitive–emotional processes (i.e., emotion regulation, attention impulsiveness, online vigilance, and multitasking) and emotional/behavioural factors (i.e., emotional problems, conduct problems, hyperactivity/inattention, peer relationships, and prosocial behaviours) that may be implicated in smartphone activities and technology addiction among adolescents. A community sample of Italian high school students completed the Smartphone Distraction Scale (SDS), the Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) for internalizing/externalizing symptoms and the Internet Addiction Test (IAT) to assess the presence and severity of IA. The scores on the SDS were found to be positively associated with IA levels. Furthermore, students exhibiting higher internalizing/externalizing symptoms, particularly those with traits of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), are more likely to manifest problematic smartphone usage. However, the study sampled only female undergraduate students. The present study sampled both male and female undergraduate students in the study area.

Sanchez-Fernandez et al. (2024) explored the interactions between generalized problematic internet use (GPIU), problematic social media use (PSMU), problematic online gaming (POG), psychological distress, and emotional well-being among university students. Therefore, the present study aimed to determine (i) the associations between problematic social media use, problematic social media use, and problematic online gaming symptoms, (ii) whether symptoms of these three problematic online behaviours form distinct entities, and (iii) whether there are associations between problematic online behaviours, psychological distress symptoms, and emotional role limitations using network analysis. A total of 807 Spanish university students participated in the study. Two network models were computed. Network 1 showed a complex interaction of nodes, with particularly strong connections between analogous symptoms of generalized problematic internet use and problematic social media use. Symptoms organized into distinct dimensions, featuring a unique dimension for problematic online gaming symptoms, one that includes preoccupation and a conflict symptom of generalized problematic internet use, and two other dimensions with symptoms of generalized problematic internet use and problematic social media use. Network 2 showed

significant connections between generalized problematic internet use and depression, generalized problematic internet use and emotional role limitations, problematic social media use and anxiety, problematic social media use and emotional role limitations, problematic online gaming and depression, and problematic online gaming and anxiety.

Suria-Martinez et al. (2024) conducted a study to firstly, understand the typology of risk players (non-risk players, players with problems, and pathological players); and secondly, to compare cognitive distortions among students with problematic profiles. Both objectives were analyzed based on the presence or absence of disability. A total of 704 students from various Spanish universities (135 with disabilities and 569 without disabilities), aged between 18 and 38, participated in the study by completing the Gamblers Belief Questionnaire (GBQ), aimed at measuring cognitive distortions related to gambling problems, as well as the Massachusetts Gambling Screen questionnaire, aimed at measuring gambling addiction. The results indicate a higher percentage of students with disabilities showing a greater risk profile for addiction. Additionally, this group of students exhibits more cognitive distortions.

Hypotheses

- i. Cognitive distortions will significantly influence internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria.
- ii. Frustration will significantly influence internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria.
- iii. Frustration will mediate between cognitive distortions and internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria.
- iv. Cognitive distortions and frustration will jointly influence internet addiction significantly among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria, when age, sex, and level of income are controlled.

Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design to investigate the mediating role of frustration in cognitive distortions and internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria. This type of design was adopted because the study intends to assess the respondents across different parameters and draw scientific inferences without any form of manipulations.

Population

The total population of undergraduate students from Joseph Sarwuan Tarka is 18, 204 (Directorate of Information and Communication Technology, 2024) while that from Benue State University is 26, 527 (Management Information System Unit; Directorate of ICT, 2024). This gives a total of 44, 731 students for the 2023/2024 academic session of the institutions. Nevertheless, not all the departments in these institutions were used, therefore the total number of students in the selected departments in Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University were 2525 while those from Benue State University were 4390. This gives a total population used as 6915.

Sample Size Determination

The sample for this study was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample determination formula. The formula is illustrated below;

$$S = \frac{X^2 NP(1-p)}{d^2(N-1) + X^2 P(1-P)}$$

Where;

S= required sample size

X = value (i.e. 1.96 for 95% confidence level)

N = population size

P = population proportion (expressed as a decimal)

d = degree of accuracy assigned to be 0.5 i.e. (5% expressed as a proportion of the margin of error)

therefore, the working is shown below;

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{1.96^2 \times 44731 \times 0.5 (1 - 0.5)}{0.05^2 (44731 - 1) + 1.96^2 \times 0.5 (1 - 0.5)} \\
 &= \frac{3.84 \times 44731 \times 0.25}{0.0025 \times 44730 + 3.84 \times 0.25} \\
 &= \frac{42941.769}{111.825 + 0.96}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{42941.76}{112.785}$$

$$= 380.7$$

$$S \approx 381$$

Therefore, based on the sample size determination formula, a sample of 381 students was used for the study.

Sampling Technique

This study used a multi-stage sampling technique. It involves the selection of participants in stages using smaller sampling units at each stage. At the initial stage, proportionate sampling was adopted to ascertain the number of participants to be drawn from each of the two universities. The sample size for the study was 381 and out of this number, 139 were drawn from Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University while 242 students were from Benue State University with respect to the selected departments. The sampling was drawn as illustrated below;

$$\text{Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University } \frac{2525}{6915} \times \frac{381}{1} = 139$$

$$\text{Benue State University } \frac{4390}{6915} \times \frac{381}{1} = 242$$

In the selection of colleges, faculties and departments, the researcher used simple random sampling technique. This was done using balloting by writing the names of the colleges/faculties of the institutions on pieces of papers with Yes/No inscription, squeezed and dropped in a container. The colleges/faculties picked with the inscription of yes were selected for consideration. The same process was done in the selection of departments from each of the faculties selected. A research assistant was asked to pick randomly from the pool of squeezed papers. Each department chosen was considered for the selection of participants. Finally, proportionate sampling was used to ascertain the number of participants to be drawn

from each department while accidental sampling (google form and physical contact) was used to sample students across the departments selected in the study.

Participants

The participants for the study comprised of 381 undergraduate students which were drawn from two (2) universities (Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University and Benue State University) all in Makurdi-Nigeria. Their demographic characteristics revealed that participants age range of between 20-32 years with a mean age of 26.055 (SD=2.361). Results further indicated that 152 (39.9%) were males while 229 (60.1%) were females. The result of participants ethnic group revealed that 201 (52.8%) were from Tiv ethnic group, 78 (20.5%) were from Idoma while 102 (26.7%) were from other ethnic groups other than those mentioned above. The result for religion shows that 293 (76.9%) were Christians, 78 (20.5%) were Muslims while 10 (2.6%) indicated that they were from other religions than those mentioned. The result also indicated that 229 (60.1%) were from medium level of income while 152 (39.9%) were from high level of income. Relatedly, results indicated that 26 (6.8%) participants were from Integrated Science Education, 35 (9.2%) were from Business Management, 38 (10.0%) were from Microbiology, 20 (5.2%) were from Crop and Soil Science, 21 (5.5%) from Forestry, 41 (10.3%) from Philosophy, 30 (7.9%) from Nursing Science, 61 (16.0%) from Business Management, 66 (17.3%) from Political Science while 44 (11.5%) were students from Mathematics and Computer Science.

Instruments

Cognitive Distortions Scale (CDS)

The Cognitive Distortions Scale was developed by Covin et al. (2011). It is a 20-item self-report measure that assesses the frequency of ten (10) dimensions of cognitive distortions (mind reading, catastrophizing, all-or-nothing thinking, emotional reasoning, labeling, mental filtering, overgeneralization, personalization, should statements, minimizing or disqualifying the positive) across both social and achievement related (e.g., school or work) situations. Participants are presented with a definition of the distortion (referred to in the questionnaire as a 'thinking type' in order to reduce defensiveness) and provided with an example of that distortion in an interpersonal and achievement context. Participants indicate the frequency with which they engage in the type of thinking on a 7-point Likert-type scale (1 = Never, 7 = All the time) in social and achievement situations. Total, social, and achievement scores are obtained by adding items. Internal consistency of each subscale was good (total frequency = .91, social frequency = .81, achievement frequency = .85, total impact = .92, social impact = .85, achievement impact = .86).

Frustration Discomfort Scale (FDS-28)

This scale was developed by Harrington (2005) and consists of 28 items. Participants are asked to rate the strength with which they hold certain beliefs on a 5-point Likert-type scale (1 = absent, 2= mild, 3= moderate, 4= strong, 5= Very strong). The scale has four subscales (emotional intolerance, entitlement, Discomfort intolerance, and achievement) with seven items in each scale. reliability and validity studies were reported for both student and clinical samples (Harrington, 2005b); Cronbach's alpha was .94 for the full scale, .88 for discomfort intolerance, .85 for entitlement, .87 for emotional intolerance, and .84 for the achievement frustration. The subscales showed unique relationships with specific psychological problems, and evidence of convergent and divergent validity.

Internet Addiction Test (IAT-20)

In this study, a modified version of the Young's internet addiction test was used (Young, 1998). It is a 20-item test with a six point range from 0 to 5. The response options are; 0 indicating did not apply, 1 indicates rarely, 2 means occasionally, 3 represents frequently, 4 indicates often and 5 represents always. The obtainable scores ranged from 0 to 100 in which higher total scores indicate excessive Internet use. Scores ranging from 0 to 30 indicates normal Internet use, 31 to 49 means mild Internet addiction, 50 to 79 stands for moderate Internet addiction and scores ranging from 80 to 100 represents severe Internet addiction (Young, 1998). The reliability coefficient Cronbach alpha of the instrument was calculated as .90.

Procedure

This study was conducted among undergraduate students of Universities in Makurdi metropolis, specifically Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University and Benue State University. The researcher sought permission from the Registrars of the above-named institutions to obtain approval to collect data among undergraduate students. Thereafter, the consent of the students was sought before the administration of the questionnaire was carried out. Before the administration of the questionnaire, the questionnaire was converted into a Google form which provided a link for participants to follow and respond to the questionnaire. The student union presidents of the selected departments were recruited as research assistants and the link to the Google form questionnaire was sent to the research assistants. The research assistants in turn forwarded the link to their respective departments. An interval of two weeks was given to participants to respond to the questionnaire. The researcher then retrieved the responses as data from his e-mail and coded it for further statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Data for this study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The researcher used descriptive statistics including frequencies and simple percentages, mean and standard deviation to summarize data on the demographic characteristics of respondents. On the other hand, Multiple linear regression analysis was used to test hypothesis one, simple linear regression analysis was used to test hypothesis two while Hayes Process Mediation analysis and Hierarchical regression analysis were used to test hypotheses three and four respectively. All the analyses were done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23.

Results

The hypotheses formulated for this study were tested using regression analysis and Process Mediation analysis. The results are presented in tables as follows:

Table 1: Summary of Multiple linear regression analysis showing the influence of cognitive distortions on internet addiction among undergraduate students of Universities in Makurdi-Nigeria

Variables	R	R ²	df	F	β	t	Sig.
Mindreading					-.094	-3.270	.001
Catastrophizing					-.305	-9.635	.000
All or nothing thinking					.195	3.396	.001
Emotional reading					.216	5.378	.000
Labeling					-.458	-11.732	.000
	.610	.372	10,370	88.835		14.928	.000
Mental filtering					.063	1.262	.008
Overgeneralization					.202	2.836	.005
Personalization					.334	2.947	.003
Should statement					-.253	-3.572	.000
Mini. or Disqualifying the Positive					-.023	-.854	.004

The result presented in table 1 indicated that cognitive distortions dimensions jointly influenced internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi Nigeria [R = .610, R²=.372, F(10,370) =88.835;p < .01]. This means that cognitive distortions accounted for 37.2% of the variance in internet addiction. On their individual contribution, the result indicated that personalization made the highest independent positive contribution to variance in internet addiction (β=.334, t=2.947; p<.01) followed by emotional reading (β=.216, t=5.378; p<.01), overgeneralization (β=.202, t=2.836; p<.01), all or nothing thinking (β=.195, t=3.396; p<.01). It was further revealed that minimizing or disqualifying the positive (β=-.023, t=-.854; p<.01), mental filtering (β=-.063, t=1.262; p<.01), mindreading (β=-.094, t=-3.270; p<.01), should statement (β=-.253, t=-3.572; p<.01), catastrophizing (β=-.305, t=-9.635; p<.01) and labeling (β=-.458, t=-11.732; p<.01) all made independent negative contributions to variance in internet addiction among undergraduate students in Makurdi metropolis. Based on finding, hypothesis one was retained.

Table 2: Summary of Simple linear regression analysis showing the influence of frustration on internet addiction among undergraduate students of Universities in Makurdi-Nigeria

Variables	R	R ²	df	F	β	t	Sig.
Constant	.493	.243	1,379	51.898		24.675	.000
Frustration					-.493	-11.041	.000

The result presented in table 2 revealed frustration significantly influenced internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi Nigeria [R=.493, R²=.243, F(1,379) =51.89;p<.01]. The further indicated that frustration accounted for 24.3% of the variance in internet addiction. This means that an increase in frustration will result in an increase in internet addiction among undergraduate students while a decrease in frustration will result in a decrease in internet addiction. Based on this finding, hypothesis two was retained.

Table 3: Summary of Hayes Process mediation analysis showing the mediating role of frustration in cognitive distortions and internet addiction among undergraduate students in Makurdi-Nigeria

Variables	R	R ²	F	Df	β	t	Sig.	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	.686	.471	168.363	3,377		26.814	.000	111.409	129.040
Cognitive distortions					.508	12.759	.000	.430	.586
Frustration					-.835	-3.879	.000	-.928	-.742
Int_1(X * M)					.173	3.666	.003	.080	.266

The result presented in table 3 shows that frustration significantly mediated the relationship between cognitive distortions and internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria [$R^2=.471$, $F(3,377)=168.363$, $Int_(X*M)$ ($\beta=.173$, $t=3.666$, $LLCI=.080$, $ULCI=.266$)]. The result further revealed that cognitive distortions made the highest significant contribution to the model ($\beta=.508$, $t=.12.759$, $LLCI=.430$, $ULCI=.586$; $p<.01$) with frustration ($\beta=-.835$, $t=-3.879$, $LLCI=-.928$, $ULCI=-.742$; $p<.01$) making the least contribution to the model. This implies that undergraduate students who are cognitively distorted and frustrated may see the internet as an escape, potentially leading to problematic usage patterns. Based on this result, hypothesis three was retained.

Table 4: Summary of hierarchical multiple regression analysis showing the joint influence of cognitive distortions and frustration among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria when age, sex and level of income are controlled

Model	Predictor	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
		β	β	β
Model 1	Age	.402**	.066	.065
Demographic variables	Sex	.616**	-1.503**	-1.479**
	Level of income	-.173**	.955**	.945**
	Model 2	Mindreading		-.037
Cognitive distortions	Catastrophizing		-.151**	-.151**
	All or nothing thinking		.221**	.212**
	Emotional reading		.133*	.137*
	Labeling		-.286**	-.275**
	Mental filtering		-.237**	-.234**
	Overgeneration		.206*	.201*
	Personalization		1.933**	1.924**
	Should statement		-.505**	-.491*
	Minimizing or disq. the positive		-.033	-.031
	Model 3	Frustration		
Frustration	R	.644	.974	.982
	R ²	.415	.947	.964
	ΔR ²	.415	.534	.410
	F	89.014	523.293	485.968
	ΔF	89.014	382.996	.987

** Significant at .01; * Significant at .05

The result presented in table 4 shows that in model 1 (step 1) when age, sex and level of income were tested, the variables jointly influenced overall internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria [$R=.644$, $R^2=.415$, $F(3,377)=89.014$, $p<.01$]. Independently, the result revealed that age ($\beta=.402$, $p<.01$), sex ($\beta=.616$, $p<.01$) and level of income ($\beta=-.173$, $p<.01$) significantly influenced internet addiction

among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria. The implication of this result is that these variables (age, sex and level of income) can contribute to problematic internet use among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi metropolis.

In model 2 cognitive distortions dimensions were introduced, the variables jointly influenced internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi - Nigeria [$R=.974$, $R^2=.949$, $F(10,367)= 523.293$, $p<.01$]. The model jointly explained 94.9% of the variance observed in internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria. This implies that undergraduate students who are cognitively distorted may not seek alternative measures of coping but rather retard to problematic internet use as a way to cope with cognitive distortions irrespective of age, sex and level of income. The result further indicated that cognitive distortions dimensions jointly contributed an additional 53.4% ($\Delta R^2=.534$) of variance in internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria after controlling for age, sex and level of income. This is a statistically significant contribution by cognitive distortions as indicated by the F-change value ($\Delta F=382.996$, $p < .01$). The result revealed that even when age, sex and level of income were controlled, cognitive distortions dimensions jointly influenced internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria.

In model 3 (step 3) when frustration was introduced, the variable significantly influenced internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi [$R=.982$, $R^2=.964$, $F(1,366)= 485.968$, $p<.01$]. This finding implies that undergraduate students who are frustrated either academically, financially or socially simply turn to the internet as a source of escapism. Model 3 as a whole explained 96.4% of the total variance observed in internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria. The result further revealed that frustration contributed an additional 41% ($\Delta R^2=.410$) of the total variance observed in internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria when age, sex and level of income are controlled. This is a statistically significant contribution by the frustration as indicated by the F-change value ($\Delta F=.987$, $p < .01$). This result indicates that even when age, sex and level of income are controlled, frustration significantly influenced internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria. This implies that undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria can be frustrated irrespective of their age, sex and level of income. Based on this result, hypothesis four was confirmed.

Discussion

Hypothesis one of this study was tested to find out if cognitive distortions influence internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria. Finding revealed that cognitive distortions positively influenced internet addiction among undergraduate students. Cognitive distortions are characterized by irrational, biased ways of thinking that can negatively impact students' emotions and behaviour. Students experiencing these symptoms often view situations in extreme terms without any middle ground, making broad conclusions based on a single event, focusing solely on the negative aspects of a situation, and ignoring any positive outcome of events. This creates a feedback loop where distorted thinking leads to maladaptive behaviours. The implication of this finding is that university students who lack adequate psychological support may be at risk of mental health issues aggravated by distorting thinking patterns including predicting negative outcomes necessitating students to seek the use of the internet as escape measures. This finding therefore agrees with Agnihotri and Datti (2023) who found a strong positive relationship

between cognitive distortions and problematic internet use. Also, Mackey and Hodgins (2022) found that cognitive distortions influence Internet gambling among students. These findings have proven that cognitive distortions can contribute to internet overuse among undergraduate students.

Hypothesis two was tested to find out if frustration influences internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi metropolis. Findings indicated that frustration positively influenced internet addiction. Frustration is characterized as an emotional response to obstacles, unmet expectations/needs, or perceived failures. Symptoms can be emotional, cognitive, behavioral, and physical. When students face academic, social, or personal stressors, they may turn to the internet as a coping mechanism, leading to excessive and compulsive internet use. The implication of this finding is that frustration from academic pressures, social conflicts, or personal struggles may lead students to seek relief in online activities like social media, gaming, or streaming. This finding corresponds with that of Shvetsova et al. (2024) who found frustration of need for achievement to contribute to the formation of internet addiction in students. Also, Aat et al. (2022) who found academic frustration to be significantly related with internet addiction among students. Similarly, Kawal and Shafi (2015) found out that male university students experienced more internet addiction and psychological distress as compared to the female university students and a significant positive correlation was found between internet addiction and psychological distress among university students.

Hypothesis three of this study was tested to find out if frustration would mediate significantly in cognitive distortions and internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria. Finding indicated that frustration significantly mediated the relationship between cognitive distortion and internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria. Frustration is a predisposing factor and as such it is expected that high levels of frustration increase students' problematic internet use. In the context of students, when frustration is relieved through internet use, the brain associates online activities with emotional relief, reinforcing the habit. This finding lacks empirical studies for discussion.

Hypothesis four of this study was tested to find out if cognitive distortions and frustration will jointly influence internet addiction significantly among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi-Nigeria when age, sex, and level of income are controlled. Findings revealed a significant joint influence of cognitive distortions and frustration on internet addiction among undergraduate students of universities in Makurdi metropolis. Finding corresponds with that of Benedetto et al. (2024) who found SDS to be positively associated with IA levels. Furthermore, students exhibiting higher internalizing/externalizing symptoms, particularly those with traits of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), are more likely to manifest problematic smartphone usage.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby suggested.

- i. Psychologists should develop and implement Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT)-Based interventions to help students identify and challenge cognitive distortions such as mind reading, catastrophizing, and emotional reasoning that contribute to problematic internet use.

- ii. Students who are experiencing these maladaptive behaviours should engage in talking to trusted friends, family members, or a counselor about struggles with frustration or internet addiction
- iii. Universities should introduce stress management programs, academic support services, and peer mentoring to help students navigate frustrating situations more effectively.

Contribution to Knowledge

The study deepens the understanding of internet addiction by exploring its psychological underpinnings, particularly the roles of cognitive distortions and frustration. It demonstrates how irrational thought patterns contribute to emotional distress, which in turn fosters excessive internet use as a maladaptive coping strategy. By identifying these mechanisms, the study provides a framework for addressing problematic internet use through targeted psychological interventions.

The study identifies frustration as a key mediator between cognitive distortions and internet addiction, offering new insights into how negative thought patterns and emotional distress interact to drive compulsive internet use. By highlighting frustration's role in this process, the research fills a gap in existing literature and provides a deeper understanding of the psychological pathways leading to internet addiction, particularly among undergraduate students.

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